

Modeling Decarbonization Pathways in the Power Sector in Developing Countries: The case of Ecuador

Authors: Jaime Guerrero, Targelia Rivadeneira, Marco Yujato

Affiliations: Ministry of Energy and Mines of Ecuador, Latin American Energy Organization

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Executive summary

In this context, a case study is presented that uses energy modeling tools to understand when and at what scale measures need to be implemented in the electricity sector to meet the growing demand for electricity and, at the same time, comply with safety and environmental constraints.

As a fundamental methodological framework, the OSeMOSYS model was used to simulate three crucial scenarios: Business-As-Usual (BAU), Energy Transition (TRN) and Energy Efficiency (EFI). Various parameters related to electricity generation, installed capacity, imports and exports, as well as national energy resources and the growing demand 2015-2070 were considered.

Figure 1 shows, the results highlight that hydro and solar energy emerge as an essential pillar to support the Ecuadorian electrical system with shares around (80 - 85) % of Hydro and solar (10 - 15) % of the total electrical generation in the different scenarios. On the other hand, system stability is evidenced by the use of natural gas in electricity generation with a share of approximately 12%, however, it entails higher costs (238 Billion US) and a more pronounced environmental impact (133 Mt CO₂). In contrast, energy efficiency emerges as the most outstanding investment, generating benefits both in terms of costs and emissions reduction (27 Mt CO₂).

Figure 1: BEN 2022, Primary Energy Production, Secondary Energy Production and Energy Demand by Sector

Therefore, this work focused on analyzing on OSeMOSYS model to support decision making in the Ecuadorian energy planning landscape.

1. Introduction

In the global energy panorama, according to data from the National Energy Balance 2022 of the Ministry of Energy and Mines of Ecuador. According to Figure 1, total primary energy production reached 203 million (BEP), where the main source of energy was oil production, representing 86% of the total, followed by renewable energy with 9% and natural gas with 5%. Regarding secondary energy production, this recorded a value of 80.43 million BEP, with electricity production being the most notable with a share of 25.4%.

On the other hand, energy consumption reached 99.9 million BEP, reflecting an increase of 18% compared to the previous year, with the transportation sector being the largest consumer with 49% of the demand, followed by the industrial sector with a 18%, and the residential sector with 13%.

It is essential to highlight the reforms implemented in the organic law of energy competitiveness and the public electric energy service. These reforms have been designed with the purpose of promoting the adoption of renewable energy sources and the implementation of efficient practices in energy consumption. In this way, it was established a legal framework that promotes the transition towards a more environmentally friendly and economically viable energy system for the country.

Consequently, our research was driven by two fundamental questions: What is the impact of the progressive substitution of heavy petroleum fuels with natural gas in thermal generation? And, how will electric mobility, industrial electrification and electric cooking initiatives affect installed capacity?

2. Methodology

The Energy Balance 2022 report of the Ministry of Energy and Mines was essential as a data source for the period 2015-2022, used in the calibration of our model. We chose OSeMOSYS to perform a long-term analysis of the energy system; This linear programming model seeks the optimal evolution of the energy-technology mix, guaranteeing minimum cost, compliance with greenhouse gas (GHG) emission limits and satisfaction of all energy demands. We used the clicSAND software as the interface to build and run the model and visualize the results (Cannone et al., 2022).

The evaluation was carried out in three scenarios: The Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, The Transition scenario (TRN) and the Energy Efficiency scenario (EFI).

In the BAU, the least-cost path is explored, maintaining the same technologies and conditions as in previous years. It is characterized by a low penetration of new technologies, no emission limits and the use of energy vectors according to historical trends.

The TRN scenario aims to explore the progressive substitution of heavy fuels with natural gas as future energy supply source, as well as achieving a 90% renewable electricity generation matrix and increase the participation of hydro, solar, wind, and biomass, as well as the introduction geothermal.

Finally, the EFI scenario seeks to incorporate e-mobility, electrification of industries (following the ISO 50001) and electric cooking, with the aim of improving energy efficiency and adapting to changes in the energy matrix.

3. Results

3.1. Overall results trends identified

Below is a table summarizing the key differences between the scenarios. The results reveal that the BAU scenario contemplates the foreseeable growth of both energy demand and supply, maintaining the use of hydropower for electricity generation.

On the other hand, the TRN scenario shows the highest total cost and higher CO2 emissions to the environment. This is due to the elimination of fossil fuels and the increased use of natural gas in electrical production to ensure the stability of the electricity system.

In contrast, the EFI scenario stands out as having the lowest total cost by reducing the use of fossil fuels. This approach results in lower CO2 emissions and minimizes the impact on the environment.

ASPECTS	Business-As-Usual (BAU) Scenario	Transition scenario (TRN)	Energy Efficiency Scenario (EFI)
Approach	Trend growth in demand for electrical energy	Transition: replacement of fossil fuels and increase in natural gas for stability of the electrical system	Inclusion of mobility, efficient cooking, ISO 50001 in the industry
Featured Power Source	Hydropower	Natural gas	Solar and Hydro mostly supply the demand
Total cost (2015-2070)	236 Billion (USD)	238 Billion (USD)	190 Billion (USD)
CO2 emissions (2070)	126 Mt CO2	133 MtCO2	27 MtCO2

3.2. Detailed analysis of results

Figure 2 shows, the behavior of electricity generation in the three scenarios highlights the predominance of electricity generation, justified by the availability of the resource, as well as the entry of new hydroelectric plants in 2032. Meanwhile, the TRN scenario begins the process of substitution with natural gas and solar generation as backup for hydropower as of 2030. Meanwhile, the EFI scenario shows a growth in demand, justified by the growth of efficient consumption in the different consumption sectors.

Figure 2: Power generation

Figure 3 shows, the evolution of the installed capacity in the (BAU) scenario reveals a maximum peak of 40 GW at the end of the period, highlighting the predominance of renewable energy sources. In addition, around 30% of the installed capacity corresponds to thermal technologies. In the Transition scenario (TRN), a slight increase in installed capacity is observed compared to the BAU. In this context, there is significant growth in the adoption of solar technologies, as well as a greater presence of natural gas. On the other hand, in the Efficiency scenario (EFI), the capacity reaches 68 GW, characterized by a marked participation of renewable technologies. It is important to highlight that the proposed model adjusts to the availability of the solar resource projected for the year 2070.

Figure 3: Installed Capacity

As anticipated and visible in Figure 3, the largest amount of CO₂ emissions are emitted in the TRN scenario due to the use of natural gas, reaching more than 133 MtCO₂ in 2070. Although this strategy can address stability issues, it presents significant environmental challenges that must be considered in decision making. While the EFI scenario highlights the reduction of emissions through the adoption of cleaner technologies, reaching 27 MtCO₂

Figure 4: Annual Emissions

When it comes to comparing the financial viability of each scenario (Figure 5), The TRN scenario is more costly with respect to the BAU and EFI scenarios, due to the increased use of natural gas in electrical production. While the cost of implementing the EFI scenario indicates that it is lower due to the better use of resources in both the supply and demand of electricity through deep energy efficiency measures such as electric mobility, efficient cooking, application of ISO 50001 standards in the industry.

Figure 5: Total Discounted Cost (2015-2070)

4. Discussion

In the TRN scenario, the option of the energy sector stability through natural gas poses environmental challenges and higher costs.

This finding highlights the need to balance system stability with considerations of sustainability and economic efficiency, suggesting that the energy transition may require more balanced and locally tailored approaches.

The EFI scenario shows energy efficiency as the best investment, with lower costs and CO2 emissions, which implies the need for policies and programs that promote energy efficiency as a central strategy to optimize resources and reduce both costs and environmental impact.

One of the limitations of the study can be considered that the results of the model are linked to the specific assumptions made during its calibration and execution, and any deviation from these assumptions could affect the validity of the projections due to the dependence on the availability and quality of the data used.

It is suggested to implement a dynamic calibration approach that allows adjusting the assumptions as new data becomes available. This helps to maintain the relevance of the

model over time, it is also recommended to use multiple data sources to reduce dependence on a single source, allowing to increase the robustness of the model.

5. Conclusion

Renewable sources, hydroelectric and solar, are fundamental elements in the Ecuadorian electricity generation matrix. Together, in the three scenarios considered, they represent more than 70% of the inputs for electricity generation. In the EFI scenario, their participation even exceeds 90%, highlighting their preponderant role in the diversification and sustainability of the energy supply.

Energy Efficiency is positioned as the most promising option in terms of investment, requiring the lowest figure of the 3 scenarios of 190 billion USD, proving to be not only economically viable, but also environmentally friendly by reducing emissions to 27 Mt CO₂. This approach emerges as the most balanced and sustainable path to Ecuador's energy future.

Energy Efficiency is positioned as the most promising investment according to the EFI scenario, proving to be economically viable, but also environmentally friendly by considerably reducing costs and CO₂ emissions. This approach is emerging as the most balanced and sustainable way forward for Ecuador's energy future.

The electrification of various uses of the demand considered in the EFI scenario represents an increase in electricity generation, which can be met by renewable resources, reaching a 98% share of generation by 2070, which translates into lower environmental impacts. This approach supports the viability and the need to continue developing and promoting the adoption of renewable energy sources to achieve a harmonious balance between energy needs and the conservation of the natural environment.

Future work includes a series of activities that will improve and strengthen the research conducted with the OSeMOSYS model. These actions will focus on the review and expansion to other sectors of the Ecuador case, verification of the flexibility of the system

using Flextool, as well as the comparison and validation of the results obtained with other models.

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Appendix:

Energy matrix of Ecuador

